

THE EFFECTS OF THE ROOT CONDITION ON STIFFNESS AND STABILITY OF DRUM DEPLOYED COMPOSITE TUBULAR BOOMS FOR SPACECRAFT

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ABSTRACT

Composite storable tubular extendable members (STEMs) have been attached to cylindrical drums to deploy deorbiting sails, sensors and other instruments in space. Attaching STEMs in this way causes the cross section to flatten at the root reducing the structural performance. This reduction in properties needs to be quantified before future high risk applications can be considered. A beam model and finite element model (FEM) are presented here to quantify the detrimental effects of attaching a STEM to a cylindrical drum by way of the rotational stiffness. The beam model is derived using a finite difference approach to numerically solve for the curvature field in the transition from the root to the free end. The FEM produced in ABAQUS uses a contact simulation to deform a composite STEM. The beam model is unable to capture the crucial partially clamped root condition, but does give a qualitative understanding of the layup effects on the stiffness. The FEM shows a significant reduction in the rotational stiffness, from 88.1Nm/rad to 14.3Nm/rad for a $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ]$ layup once the STEM is attached to the drum. The braid angle of a $[\pm \theta^\circ/0^\circ/\pm \theta^\circ]$ layup is shown to have a lesser effect on the stiffness with larger braid angles increasing the rotational stiffness by 2Nm/rad due to the shorter transition length.

1 INTRODUCTION

The expansion of the space industry in recent decades has instigated technological advances in both materials and structures. An excellent example of the numerous technological improvements is the progression of storable tubular extendable members (STEMs) to composite STEMs. The benefits in moving to composite STEMs are the potential for tailoring the thermal and mechanical properties. The cross section of STEMs has traditionally been of the form of overlapped tubing, but with smaller included angles they resemble a carpenter's tape [1]. Historically, small included angled STEMs have been deployed from cylindrical drums, shown in Figure 6, and have deployed sensors, antennas, deorbiting sails and solar sails spanning distances of metres. Recently, composite STEMs have been used to successfully deploy deorbiting sails at the Surrey Space Centre (SSC) [2], and the harpoon target on the RemoveDebris mission [3]. Naturally engineers are now considering further applications for composite STEMs.

One such application is the deployment of a secondary mirror for an Earth observation (EO) Cassegrain telescope. This application has already been proposed in a hexapod configuration in [4], and other slight STEM variations in [5]. The benefit of deploying such a telescope in orbit is that the focal length does not need to be maintained during the harsh launch phase. Additionally, there will be a volume saving in the launch vehicle and potential for having larger telescopes mounted on smaller satellite platforms. This will make them more accessible to researchers and small businesses. There is,

of course, the obvious detriment of increasing the complexity of the system. STEMs naturally alleviate some of this complexity due to their ability to self-deploy.

There are two key requirements for the design of a deployable telescope: the deployed stiffness and deployed thermal stability. The deployed stiffness must be sufficiently high to prevent micro-vibrations, generated from instruments such as reaction wheels, from distorting images. Likewise, the materials used in the design must prevent micron level thermal distortions as the temperature varies during orbit. Composite STEMs have the potential to meet both requirements by tailoring the layup to increase the stiffness and lower the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE). The stiffness will be the focus of this paper herein.

Composite tapes, STEMs of a short length, have been found to show linear moment-rotation behaviour up until a snap through moment is reached [6-8]. The tapes investigated were rigidly held with fully deployed ends and bent to form folds at the middle of the length. Figure 1 shows that the drum attached end of deployed STEMs is flattened due to bolting, which complicates any analysis.

Figure 1: Composite STEM flattened by bolting to a cylindrical drum, after [15].

The geometry of a traditional STEM's transition region is modelled in [7,14]. Both methods use uniform boundary conditions to produce closed form solutions. Again, the complexity of introducing the drum at the root is neglected in this case as it is only the transition region during deployment that is of interest. Extensive research into the stiffness and buckling of STEMs and composite STEMs has been conducted [9]. In this work there is also a consideration as to the effects of the partially flattened root reducing the geometric properties of a STEM. With applications directly related to the space industry, [10,11] investigated the effects of the composite layup on the dynamic performance of composite STEMs and the snap-through moment when subjected to spacecraft manoeuvres. In [10,11] the composite STEMs were modelled with a fully clamped fully formed root condition, and hence avoided modelling the effects of attachment to a cylindrical drum.

In [15] the root condition issue was mitigated by making the deployment drum height less than the arc length of the boom, shown in Figure 1. This allowed the edges of the section to partially form, increasing the second moment of area at the root, and hence the stiffness. More recently, Rocco [12] have designed a composite STEM deployer that allows a fully formed and fully clamped root condition. While this works well for their application of deploying embedded solar sails, it is likely limited to shallow included angles that avoid sharp changes in curvature. The reader may consider a drum with rounded edges as this would allow more forming of the edges. However, this reduces the amount of zero curvature area to restrain the boom on the drum. Attachment of the boom onto a non-zero curved region would result in Rocco's solution.

The literature indicates that the root condition of a drum deployed composite STEM will affect the stiffness properties, but that for simplification purposes it is often neglected. To design a stiff composite STEM deployed telescope these effects must be understood and quantified. This paper will investigate the effects of a composite STEM's rotational stiffness with reference to a composite layup for a given drum height. The paper is split into two sections. First, a simple beam model will be

presented that includes the change in cross section at the root, which illustrates the detrimental effects of the partial flattening on the rotational stiffness. Second, a finite element model (FEM) is used to predict the rotational stiffness. A range of braid angles in a $[\pm\theta^\circ/0^\circ/\pm\theta^\circ]$ layup will be investigated using the FEM.

2 A BEAM MODEL

Given what has been stated previously regarding existing literature not accounting for the partial clamping at the root, it may seem counterintuitive to include a beam model in this paper. However, the purpose of the beam model is to demonstrate, by inclusion of the partially flattened root cross section, the detrimental effects on the rotational stiffness. Additionally, it will give an indication as to whether the cross section or the restraining root condition impacts the stiffness the most. Finally, it justifies the need for a finite element approach.

The first step in the beam model was to calculate the properties of the composite with a $[\pm\theta^\circ/0^\circ/\pm\theta^\circ]$ layup. Ideally the properties for the braid laminate would come from manufacturer's data or by testing samples. However, due to the large number of samples that would be required to characterise the braid with angles between 20° and 70° , this was not possible. Instead, a technique used by other researchers [11,13] was utilised that placed two opposite angled plies on the same layer with half the mechanical properties. For example, a $\pm 30^\circ$ would consist of one $+30^\circ$ and one -30° ply with half the properties on the same layer.

The next step was to predict the shape of the transition between the partially flattened root and fully formed boom end. This was determined using the second order partial differential equation found in [7,14], Equation 1:

$$\partial^2 \kappa_2 / \partial x^2 + \beta^2 \partial^2 \kappa_2 / \partial y^2 = 0 \quad (1)$$

Where κ_2 is the transverse curvature, neglecting the longitudinal curvature, and β^2 is given by Equation 2.

$$\beta^2 = D_{22} / (D_{12} + 2 * D_{66}) \quad (2)$$

Where D_{ij} are the bending stiffness (\underline{D}) properties of the composite. In [14] Equation 1 was solved analytically using uniform boundary conditions. However, in the case of Figure 1, the boundary conditions at the cylindrical drum are more complex. Therefore, Equation 1 was solved using the finite difference method (the central difference scheme) and so Equation 1 becomes Equation 3.

$$(\kappa_{i-1,j} - 2 * \kappa_{i,j} + \kappa_{i+1,j}) / h^2 + \beta^2 * (\kappa_{i,j-1} - 2 * \kappa_{i,j} + \kappa_{i,j+1}) / k^2 = 0 \quad (3)$$

Where the subscript 2 on the transverse curvature variable is omitted for simplicity, i and j refer to horizontal and vertical grid points respectively, and h and k denote the distance between horizontal and vertical grid points, respectively. The boundary condition along the length of a given drum height was set to zero and all other edges were set to the deployed curvature. Matlab was used to construct and solve the system of equations to produce a transverse curvature field, an example of which is shown in Figure 2. Also observed in Figure 2 are the boundary conditions with the partially flattened region, corresponding to the bolted root end on the left, while the remaining edges are the deployed curvature. For context the boom shown in Figure 2 has a deployed radius of 17.5 mm and included angle of 180° .

Figure 2: Numerically solved curvature field for a boom attached to a drum on the left hand edge.

With the curvature field approximated, the second moment of area needed to be calculated for a given boom. Of course, in this case, the second moment of area is a function of the distance along the boom, and is also non-uniform across the section. The non-uniform cross section was simplified into three arcs, one central arc and two edge arcs. The justification for this simplification was drawn from practical observations. The central arc was assigned the curvature of a point on the centreline of the curvature field, κ_c , while the two tails take on the deployed curvature, κ_t . Figure 4 shows the approximated cross section at two points along the length of the beam for clarification.

Figure 3: Cross section approximations at two points on the length of the STEM.

Using the approximated cross section geometry the second moment of area was calculated at the discrete points along the length of the boom. Then, the Matlab function ODE45 was used to numerically integrate the Euler-Bernoulli beam equation, Equation 4, to produce the angular rotation at the end of the boom, α .

$$\alpha = \int F^*(x-L)/E_x * I_{yy}(x) dx \quad (4)$$

Where F is the applied load, L is the length of the boom, E_x is the longitudinal modulus and I_{yy} is the second moment of area about the Y axis. The rotational stiffness, k_{rot} , was then evaluated using Equation 5:

$$k_{rot} = F * L / \alpha \quad (5)$$

Also of interest in this analytical model is the transition length, which is defined in this paper as the length from the bolted region to the point where the curvature is less than 10% of the deployed curvature. This was determined using the central curvature vector, shown in Figure 4.

3 FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

Several methods were considered for modelling a drum attached composite STEM in ABAQUS. A contact simulation was chosen as it represented the complex shape and boundary conditions well. The simulation contained two separate parts: the STEM and the drum shown in Figure 4. Note that only half the boom and drum were modelled as the natural symmetry was exploited to simplify the problem and reduce computational time.

Figure 4: Half the modelled STEM and drum in ABAQUS.

The drum was set as a rigid body while the STEM material was assigned using a composite layup. The calculated braid properties were the same as in the beam model. The composite STEM used general purpose S4R elements, as is common in previous literature. The washer area, taken as an M2 washer from [15], was positioned so that it was in the middle of the drum once the STEM was deformed.

Excluding the initial step, the ABAQUS simulation was comprised of four steps: flattening, applied bolt load, release constraints and applied load. In the flattening stage a displacement was applied to the drum to simulate pressing it onto the STEM. Next, a bolt load was applied to an M2 washer sized area of the STEM to simulate the preloading of an M2 bolt. The constraints that held the STEM in place for the previous two steps were then released and the STEM was simultaneously fixed in all directions and rotations at the washer area. Finally, a shell edge load was applied to the end of the STEM. The rotational stiffness was calculated by extracting the rotation in the relevant direction of the central end node, shown in Figure 4, and setting this equal to α in Equation 5. Note that the rotation was extracted at the start and end of the applied load step to compensate for any previous movement of the STEM during the previous steps. Because only half of the STEM was modelled the applied shell load, defined in N/mm, was half of the value that would be applied to a complete STEM. Thus, when the rotational stiffness was calculated the applied load was doubled. Due to the extensive rotation of the shell elements the non-linear geometry option was turned on. All of the steps were of the static general type and the ABAQUS solver was ABAQUS standard.

In an attempt to understand the beam model, an additional simplified FEM was created in which the restrained region, once deformed by the drum and bolt load, was the entire cross section and not just the washer area. This boundary condition would be the same as the beam model and would allow

a direct comparison. The differences between the two restraining methods are shown in Figure 5 where the shaded regions symbolise the restrained regions.

Figure 5: Clamped cross section boundary condition, left, and washer restrained boundary condition, right.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 BEAM MODEL

The material used for the composite in this study consisted of a E-glass fibre reinforced with polypropylene (PP). The mechanical properties for a glass-PP UD ply are given in Table 1, where the ply thickness, t , is 0.3mm. The directions are defined in Figure 6 where E_1 is the longitudinal modulus and E_2 the transverse modulus. The glass-PP UD material properties were sourced from TICONA, CFR-TP PP GF70-13.

Figure 6: Drum attached composite STEM with coordinate system and braid angle definition.

Material	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	G (GPa)	ν_{12}
<i>Glass-PP</i>	28	4	1.39	0.4

Table 1: Mechanical properties for a glass-PP ply.

The composite STEM layup was chosen as $[\pm\theta/0^\circ/\pm\theta^\circ]$, which is in line with previous work. The geometry of the STEMs is summarised in Table 2. For all of the following analysis the drum height was set to 25mm.

Included angle	Internal radius	Arc length	Length
γ	r	s	L
($^\circ$)	(mm)	(mm)	(mm)
180	17.5	55	300

Table 2: Composite STEM geometric properties.

Using the material properties for braid angles between 20° and 70° the rotational stiffness was calculated iteratively using the procedure set out in Section 2. The results of this are shown in Figure 7. Also plotted in Figure 7 is the maximum rotational stiffness of a corresponding STEM that is not bolted to a deployment drum, and hence is not partially flattened at the root. A comparison shows that the rotational stiffness is reduced with the introduction of the drum. The reduction is not negligible and it should be noted that the reduction is solely due to the inclusion of the geometric changes at the root. A greater disparity between the results is observed for smaller braid angles because the transition length is largest in this region. Figure 7 begins to illustrate the magnitude of the detrimental effects the drum has on the structural performance of composite STEMs.

Figure 7: Drum deployed and non-drum deployed rotational stiffness against braid angle for a $[\pm\theta^\circ/0^\circ/\pm\theta^\circ]$ layup calculated using the beam model.

Additionally, Figure 7 shows that the rotational stiffness reaches a minimum at a braid angle of 50° , corresponding to a layup of $[\pm 50^\circ/0^\circ/\pm 50^\circ]$. This is not necessarily an intuitive result because at first glance it would be expected that the lowest longitudinal stiffness layup would yield the lowest rotational stiffness, and hence the two curves presented in Figure 7 would follow the same trend. It can be seen with the aid of the vertical line at 50° that this is not the case. Therefore, there is an additional variable that determines the rotational stiffness of a drum deployed composite STEM.

Figure 8, shows the predicted transition length for the layups investigated as well as the longitudinal stiffness of the layups. The longitudinal modulus curve matches well with the no drum rotational stiffness shown in Figure 7. This is because this is the only changing variable for this calculation. The introduction of the drum results in a transition region where the STEM is flattened at the root so the transverse properties contribute to the rotational stiffness. At braid angles approaching 70° the transition length is at its shortest, shown in Figure 8. So, while the longitudinal modulus is approximately the same for the 50° and 70° layup the transition length for the 50° layup is almost double, which results in the lower rotational stiffness.

Figure 8: Transition length and longitudinal modulus against braid angle for a $[\pm\theta/0^\circ/\pm\theta]$ layup.

Conceptually, the shorter transition length can be attributed to the larger braid angles resisting flattening of the cross section due to a larger E_2 value. However, analysis of the curvature field equation gives a more analytical explanation. The β^2 term in Equation 3 defines the transition length and a normalised plot of β^2 and the transition length, reveals an inversely proportional relationship, shown in Figure 9. The β^2 term is a function of \mathbf{D} matrix terms and, specifically, is proportional to the D_{22} term. So as the braid angles become larger there is a greater resistance to bending in the transverse direction. Note that the staggered nature of the transition length curves is a result of the discretisation in calculating the curvature field.

Figure 9: Normalised β^2 and normalised transition length against braid angle for a $[\pm\theta/0^\circ/\pm\theta]$ layup.

4.2 FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

Using the FEM described in Section 3 with the mechanical and geometric properties in Table 1 and Table 2, the rotational stiffness was calculated iteratively for braid angles between 20° and 70°. The rotational stiffness was also calculated for a STEM deformed in the same manner as described in Section 3, but clamped completely across the cross section. Figure 5 shows the difference in restraining methods between the two ABAQUS simulations. Figure 10 shows the rotational stiffness results for the washer restrained and clamped cross section STEMs.

Figure 10: Rotational stiffness with washer clamped and cross section clamped conditions from ABAQUS simulations against braid angle for a $[\pm\theta^\circ/0^\circ/\pm\theta^\circ]$ layout.

It is clear to see in Figure 10 there is a large disparity between the washer clamped and cross section clamped simulations. This result was expected owing to there being a large difference between restraining a region of the STEM, the washer area, and the entire cross section. While expected, this significant difference quantifies the detrimental effect that attaching a composite STEM to a cylindrical drum has on the structural performance. Therefore, it is clear that the effect cannot be ignored, particularly for the high stiffness requirements of a deployable telescope.

The additional purpose of conducting the simulations with a completely clamped cross section was to allow comparisons with the derived beam model, as it is clear the beam model is not able to capture the important partial restraining of the cross section. Figure 11 shows the rotational stiffness calculated from the beam model (the same as the blue line in Figure 7), and the clamped ABAQUS simulations (the same as the orange line in Figure 10). Also included in Figure 11 is the transition length predicted by both methods. Figure 11 shows that the two models are in good agreement with one another, and that the transition lengths follow a similar overall trend. The good agreement is a result of the boundary conditions being the same.

Figure 11: Beam and clamped ABAQUS rotational stiffness and predicted transition lengths braid angle for a $[\pm\theta^\circ/0^\circ/\pm\theta^\circ]$ layout.

There are a number of explanations as to why the results are not in perfect agreement. First, the boundary condition assumptions used to derive the curvature field for the beam model are approximate. Referring back to Figure 2, it was assumed the curvature everywhere but the drum region took on the deployed curvature, $1/r$. However, on examination of the curvature field in ABAQUS there exists a region in which the STEM curves more at the edge of contact on the cylindrical drum (the red region in Figure 12). This has the effect of increasing the second moment of area directly at the root making the STEM stiffer. Furthermore, this effect can be seen in the transition length for the ABAQUS model, which is longer than the beam model, particularly at the extremes of the braid angles.

Figure 12: Increased change in curvature, red, due to the edge of the drum.

Second, the simplification of the geometry in the beam model as three arcs causes the STEM to be geometrically more compliant. This is because taking the central arc to have the curvature associated with the central vector, see Figure 4, means the true geometry of the cross section is not represented in this region. As an example, in Figure 4, if the curvature of the central vector at $x=50\text{mm}$ is approximated as 45m^{-1} , when moving away towards the edge the curvature quickly reaches its maximum value, 57m^{-1} , which is unaccounted for in the simplified beam model.

Returning to the ABAQUS washer clamped results, Figure 13 shows the variation of the rotational stiffness, principal material moduli and transition length with braid angle for a $[\pm\theta/0^\circ/\pm\theta^\circ]$ layup. The rotational stiffness can be seen to increase with braid angle due to the increase in transverse modulus. This relationship was also seen in the beam model via the β^2 term causing a decrease in transition length with braid angle. Changes in the transition length and material properties are clearly dwarfed by the boundary condition effects given that the rotational stiffness range in Figure 13 is $\pm 2\text{Nm/rad}$, while the difference between restraining methods in Figure 10 for a $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ]$ layup is a reduction from 88.1Nm/rad to 14.3Nm/rad .

Figure 13: Washer restrained ABAQUS simulation rotational stiffness, principal moduli and transition length against braid angle for a $[\pm\theta^\circ/0^\circ/\pm\theta^\circ]$ layup.

5 CONCLUSION

This paper has attempted to quantify the effects of restraining a composite STEM on a cylindrical drum via the rotational stiffness. A beam model was derived and the rotational stiffness was calculated for a range of braid angles in a $[\pm\theta^\circ/0^\circ/\pm\theta^\circ]$ layup. A FEM was presented that used ABAQUS to predict the rotational stiffness of a composite STEM. The FEM used a contact simulation to deform the STEM using a rigid drum, apply a bolted preload and then apply an end load. With a clamped cross section the rotational stiffness results between the FEM and beam model are in good agreement. However, comparisons between the beam model and washer restrained ABAQUS simulation show the beam model to be inadequate, as it is unable to capture the non-uniform restraining of the STEM's cross section. The restraining condition has been shown to influence the rotational stiffness by almost an order of magnitude. A decrease in transition length of the STEMs, which is a function of the material properties, is shown to increase the rotational stiffness. However, the effect of completely clamping the STEM's root is much more pronounced and it should be endeavoured to achieve a clamped condition in the design of a deployable telescope.

REFERENCES

- [1] F.P.J. Rimrott and G. Fritzsche, Fundamentals of STEM Mechanics, *IUTAM-IASS Symposium on Deployable Structures: Theory and Applications*, 2000, pp.321-333.
- [2] A. Viquerat, M. Schenk, V. Lappas and B. Sanders, Functional and Qualification Testing of the InflateSail Technology Demonstrator, *2nd AIAA Spacecraft Structures Conference, Kissimmee, Florida, January, 2015* (doi: <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2015-1627>).

- [3] J. Forshaw, G.S. Aglietti, N. Navarathinamb, H. Kadhemb, T. Salmonc, A. Pisseloupc, E. Joffred, T. Chabote, I. Retatf, R. Axthelmf, S. Barracloughg, A. Ratcliffeg, C. Bernalh, F. Chaumettei, A. Pollinij and W.H. Steyn, RemoveDEBRIS: An in-orbit active debris removal demonstration mission, *Acta Astronautica*, **127**, 2016, pp. 448-463 (doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2016.06.018>).
- [4] G. Aridon, D. Rémond, F. Morestin, L. Blanchard and R. Dufour, Self-Deployment of a Tape-Spring Hexapod: Experimental and Numerical Investigation, *Journal of Mechanical Design*, **131**, 2009 (doi: 10.1115/1.3042148).
- [5] P. Zhong, C. Li, N. Jing, Y. Chong and G. Ren, Research on lightweight passive deployment mechanism for the secondary mirror in the deployable space telescope, *Proceedings Volume 9685, 8th International Symposium on Advanced Optical Manufacturing and Testing Technologies: Design, Manufacturing, and Testing of Micro- and Nano-Optical Devices and Systems; and Smart Structures and Materials*, Suzhou, China, 2016, pp. 1-10.
- [6] K. Seffen and S. Pellegrino, Deployment dynamics of tape springs, *Proceedings of the Royal Society A*, **455**, 1999, pp. 1003-1048 (doi: 10.1098/rspa.1999.0347).
- [7] K. Seffen, B. Wang and S. Guest, Folded orthotropic tape-springs, *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, **123**, 2019, pp. 138-148 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmps.2018.09.017>).
- [8] S. Walker and G. Aglietti, A study of tape spring fold curvature for space deployable structures, *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers*, **221**, 2007, pp. 313-325.
- [9] J.M. Fernandez, *Low-Cost Gossamer Systems for Solar Sailing & Spacecraft Deorbiting Applications*, PhD Thesis, 2014, University of Surrey.
- [10] C.Wu and A. Viquerat, Natural frequency optimization of braided bistable carbon/epoxy tubes: Analysis of braid angles and stacking sequences, *Composite Structures*, **159**, 2017, pp. 528-537 (doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2016.09.075>).
- [11] C.Wu and A. Viquerat, Computational and experimental study on dynamic instability of extended bistable carbon/epoxy booms subjected to bending, *Composite Structures*, **188**, 2018, pp. 347-355 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2018.01.029>).
- [12] D. Turse, L. Adams, K. Medina and T. Rose, Design, Analysis and Testing of a Composite Beam Roll-Out Array (COBRA) for Small Satellites, *AIAA SciTech Forum, San Diego, California, January 7-11, 2019*, pp. 1-13 (doi: 10.2514/6.2019-2024).
- [13] G. Knott and A. Viquerat, Curved Bistable Composite Slit Tubes with Positive Gaussian Curvature, *AIAA Journal*, **56**, 2018, pp. 1679-1688 (doi: 10.2514/1.J056411).
- [14] L. Yang, H. Tan and Z. Cao, Modeling and analysis of the ploy region of bistable composite cylindrical shells, *Composite Structures*, **192**, 2018, pp. 347-354 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2018.02.085>).
- [15] J. Fernandez, M. Schenk, G. Prassinios, V. Lappas and S. Erb, deployment mechanisms of a gossamer satellite deorbiter, *15th European Space Mechanisms and Tribology Symposium, Noordwijk, The Netherlands, September, 2013*.